

Research

CEO Duality and Risk: A Case of Textile Firms Listed on Pakistan Stock Exchange

Mahboob Ullah^{}, Niaz Mohammad Hamdard², Noor Ahmad Sahar³*

¹Associate Professor, Faculty of Management Sciences, Al-Taqwa University, Nangarhar, Afghanistan

²Assistant Professor, Faculty of Public Administration and Policy, Nangarhar University, Afghanistan

³Assistant Professor, Faculty of Public Administration and Policy, Nangarhar University, Afghanistan

***Corresponding author**

Accepted: 01 October, 2019; Online: 12 November, 2019

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3539678>

Abstract: Sound governance system can inculcate investors' confidence. Good practices of corporate governance craft the iconic position of corporations by making performance strong and reducing risk. The fundamental purpose of this study was to evaluate the influencing role of CEO Duality on risk of Textile manufacturing corporations listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX). For achievement of research objective, twenty Textile sectors firms listed on the PSX was employed from the period 2010 to 2018. Hypotheses were tested by deploying correlation analysis and fixed effect regression model, and results were tested via Best Linear Un-biased Estimator properties of regression. The findings reveal that CEO duality has positive association with solvency risk. The study support the hypothesis and preceding studies that have also documented positive relation between CEO Duality and risk. This study is imperative for Textile sector firms in developing economies like Pakistan in understanding the importance of corporate governance practices as CEO duality increases corporate risk and lose investor trust in under developing country like Pakistan.

Keywords: CEO Duality, Risk, Pakistan Stock Exchange

Introduction

One of the major fields of business is corporate governance, which boost investors' confidence and protect stakeholders' interest. Investors have identified the importance of corporate governance system at national and international level (Owen, 2003). Corporate governance has got great concentration in developing and under developed economies (Mallin,

2004; Reed, 2002; Solomon & Solomon, 2004). Due to financial scandals in underdeveloped countries, corporate governance has given much consideration (Baydoun, Maguire, Ryan & Willett, 2013). Many developing countries have also given more concentration as many of these countries lack appropriate corporate governance practices (Ekanayake, Perera & Perera, 2010). Pakistan is an underdeveloped country and the Securities and Exchange Commission of Pakistan (SECP) is focusing on proper implementation of corporate governance mechanism after issuing the code of corporate governance in 2002 as it plays a significant role in economic development.

SECP has made corporate governance obligatory for all potential listed firms on Pakistan Stock Exchange in order to instill confidence of investors, ensure transparency, accountability and safeguard the interest of all stakeholders in particular of minority stakeholders. The code of corporate governance varies from country to country. USA, UK and rest of English speaking countries follow Anglo Saxon system of corporate governance and Germany, France and Spain use European Continental system of corporate governance. Pakistan corporate governance system is based on Anglo Saxon system. In Anglo Saxon system of corporate governance, one independent board of directors monitors and controlled the entire functions of management for increasing shareholders value. A very few people possess the legal authority over management team and minority investors own very low protection, who look to the support of independent director (Hasan, 2009).

The corporations try to magnetize investors across the world by offering comparative sound return. The goal of corporation and other stakeholders (lenders, business associates, employees and government) are achieved by applying good corporate governance system. Good governed companies produce good return to all stakeholders including shareholders. Poor governed corporations cannot attain profit and hence cannot meet operating needs and other financial requisites and become insolvent. Corporate governance is the mechanism used for sound performance (Ghabayen, 2012). According to (John, Litov & Yeung, 2005), application of corporate governance system mitigates risk and managers invest in riskier but advantageous projects.

This study examine the influence of one of the significant facet of corporate governance: CEO duality on solvency risk of Textile firms listed on PSX from 2010 to 2018. The code of corporate governance of Pakistan requires that one person should not hold dual positions; position of CEO and chairperson in the company. Studies have proved a positive association

between CEO duality and solvency risk in developed and under-developed countries. This study also investigates the influence of CEO duality on solvency risk of listed Textile firms on PSX from the period of 2010 to 2018.

Literature Review

Corporate governance plays a substantial role in every sector across the globe due to emergence of markets, liberation of trade, financial crises and scandals, development of technology and mobility of capital. Corporate bodies are required to be governed as per the codes of corporate governance prevailing in the country. The system of corporate governance varies from country to country and applied in the world (Hasan, 2009). Outsider system of corporate governance (Unitary System) is followed in United State and English speaking countries, whereas, Insider Model (Dual System) of corporate governance is applied in European countries (Germany) (Nestor Thompson, 2000). Both the systems of corporate governance have developed from different regulatory, political and institutional environments (Babic, 2003). Outsiders Model of corporate governance inclined towards corporate managers' reward and control, while Insider Model of corporate governance relies upon controlling the behavior of managers and owners (Shleifer & Vishny, 1997). There is insider system of corporate governance in Pakistan and Germany. However, Uni-boarded system exist in Pakistan, whereas companies have supervisory and management board. For the very first time, the system of corporate governance was introduced in USA in 1970 while the Securities and Exchange Commission of Pakistan firstly notified the codes of corporate governance in March 2002 that has been upgrading time to time based on the national and international market demand.

Traditionally the system of corporate governance is concerned with shareholders (principals) and managers (agents) conflict. Jensen and Meckling, (1976) describes in Agency Theory that the conflict arises when principal assign the corporate operation to agents. The principals expect agents for successfully operation of firm in the best interest of firm, however, the interest of agent deviate from the principal interest that causes more problems in the organization. Due to interest divergence, firm may bear financial and non-financial risks including solvency risk. Solvency risk effect corporate stakeholders. Stakeholders interest collide often times. A few hold greater control in corporate decisions. Therefore, a system is required which can preserve the interest of each stakeholder from exploitation form individual

stakeholder's decision. Butt, (2012) describe that corporate governance is the system employed in companies for getting the interest of each stakeholder. The mechanism applied in order to direct and control firm activities is termed as corporate governance (Australian Standard, 2003). The central purpose of corporate governance system is directing and controlling for bringing precision in firms which impact performance and risk of corporation. Separation of firm's ownership and control is the fundamental reason of the agency conflict, which demands for effective implication of corporate governance mechanism. The firms adhering the codes of corporate governance accomplish its objectively easily whereas, those firms do not exercise the corporate governance practices bear risk. Saito, (2008) defined risk as the chances that actual return deviates from expected return. Roggi, Garvey and Damodaran, (2012) linked risk to the expectation of human beings, furthermore they grouped risk into controllable (unsystematic) risk and uncontrollable (systematic) risk. Uncontrollable risk is market risk which affects the entire economy not an individual firm and firms are affected due to external factors (high inflation, interest and recession). Uncontrollable risk cannot be controlled but can be mitigated via diversification. Controllable risk is the business risk which is affected due to corporate inside factors (Aggarwal & Samwick, 1999). Corporate governance effect corporate risk (Prasetyo, 2011). Good corporate governance system can minimize corporate business risk. Sound corporate governance system improves efficiency of managers, reduce risk, boost stakeholders' worth and get competitive advantage.

The code of corporate governance of Pakistan (2018) requires that CEO must not hold the position of chairperson. Studies have proved that CEO duality has positive association with solvency risk (Mayers & Smith, 2010; Rogers, 2002; Sharpe & Stadnik, 2007). Agyei and Owusu, (2014) conducted a study on Ghanaian listed manufacturing companies from year 2008 to 2012 to check the influence of CEO duality on solvency risk. The outcomes of their studies revealed a positive association between CEO duality and risk. They described further that one person controlling both the position causes increase in risk. Ullah et al., (2017) conducted a research to check the impact of corporate governance: board independence, board size and CEO duality on solvency risk of cement firms listed on PSX from year 2005 to 2014. The outcomes proved a positive association between CEO duality and solvency risk whereas a negative relation between board independence and board size, and solvency risk. The basic objective of this study was to analyze the effect of CEO Duality on solvency risk of Textile manufacturing corporations

on PSX from 2010 to 2018 and recommend indicators for mitigating solvency risk. In this research CEO Duality is defined as one person perform dual role in the organization mean that one person performing the role of chairperson and chief executive officer duality, whereas solvency risk is calculated with times interest earned and defined as earnings before interest and taxes, and measured as earnings before interest and taxes divided by interest expenses. For accomplishment of research objective, the hypothesis is developed as;

H₁: CEO duality and solvency risk have positive association.

The given below model is developed on the basis of proceeding works of (Agyei & Owusu, 2014; Azeem, Hassan & Kouser, 2013;).

Figure No.1. Model

Data Analysis

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences 21 is deployed for the descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation and linear regression analyses of the facets of CG, CS and risk. The sample of 20 Textile sector firms enlisted on the PSX from 2010 to 2018 is chosen for this study. Based on the nature of study, quantitative technique and deductive approached is used. Data regarding CEO duality and solvency risk is ascertained from the audited annual reports of these firms. The data regarding CEO Duality and solvency risk is analyzed by deploying descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and fixed effect regression model using SPSS21.

Model Equations

In this model, Solvency Risk is regressed on CEO Duality (See Table 3).

$$\text{Solvency Risk} = \pi + \beta_1 \{\text{CEOD}\} + \mu t \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

In this equation, CEOD denotes CEO Duality, π constant, β denotes beta and μt denotes the error term.

Results and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

The descriptive statistics of CEO Duality and solvency risk is documented in given Table 1. The minimum means values are 0.01 to 1.01 whereas the 0.97 to 1.49 for standard deviation that shows that variables were operated for use.

Table 1: *Internal Consistency and Reliability (N=200)*

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
CEO Duality	0.17	0.38	0.01	1.01
Solvency Risk	1.49	0.39	0.97	1.49

Correlation Analysis

Solvency Risk and CEO Duality. The results of solvency risk with CEO Duality in below Table 2 reveals that CEO duality has positive association with solvency risk (0.34).

Table 2: *Correlation Analysis: Risk with CEO Duality*

	CEO Duality	Solvency Risk
CEO Duality	--	
Times Interest Earned	0.35**	--

Regression Analysis

The hypothesis is tested by using fixed effect regression model to analyze the association between CEO duality and solvency risk. The CEO duality is exogenous variable whereas solvency risk is outcome variable.

CEO Duality and Solvency Risk. The outcomes of equation 1 are shown in Table 3 that shows the impact of CEO Duality with solvency risk. The results are robust and indicates that $R^2=0.45$ that shows 45% change in solvency risk due to CEO duality. The results also prove that F value=6.43 at $P < 0.05$. The outcomes documents beta value of 0.25 and t value 2.09 for CEO duality. The results demonstrate CEO duality has positive effect on solvency risk. The outcomes of this research support the hypothesis that CEO duality positively influences solvency risk. The results of current study are in line with earlier studies that have proved a positive association

between CEO duality and solvency risk (Agyei & Owusu, 2014; Mayers & Smith, 2010; Rogers, 2002; Sharpe & Stadnik, 2007).

Table 3: Regression Analysis: CEO Duality and Solvency Risk

	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P	[95% Conf. Interval]	
CEO Duality	0.25	0.35	2.09	0.04	-05.40	5.90
Number of observations				=	200	
F Value				=	6.43	
P Value				=	0.00	
R ²				=	0.45	

Note: **= p<0.01, *= p<0.05

Conclusion

The result revealed that solvency risk is significantly affected by the CEO Duality. There are several evidences of hypothesis used in this study that CEO Duality positively affects solvency risk. The analysis presents evidence that CEO duality positively affects solvency risk. The outcomes reveal that firms with CEO duality bear more solvency risk and in particular to Textile sector firms listed on Pakistan Stock Exchange. The code of corporate governance of Pakistan (2018) also requires firm to have separate individuals for chairperson and CEO of the firm which in turn minimize risk. This study proves the previous research work done the relationship between CEO duality and solvency risk (Anderson & Reeb, 2003; Cheng, Evans & Nagarajan, 2008; Wahla, Shah & Hussain, 2012).

REFERENCES

- Abbott, L. J., Park, Y., & Parker, S. (2000). The effects of audit committee activity and independence on corporate fraud. *Managerial Finance*, 26 (11), 55-68.
- Aggarwal, R. K., & Samwick, A. A. (1999). The other side of the trade-off: the impact of risk on executive compensation. *Journal of Political Economy*, 107(1), 65-106.
- Agyei, A., & Owusu, R. A. (2014). The effect of ownership structure and corporate Governance on capital structure of Ghanaian listed manufacturing companies. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*,4(1), 109-118.

- Anderson, R. C., & Reeb, D. M. (2003). Founding-family ownership and firm performance: evidence from the S & P 500. *Journal of Finance*, 58 (3), 1301-1328.
- Australian Standard, (2003). *Good governance principles, AS8000-2003*, Sydney: Standards Australia International.
- Azeem, M., Hassan, M., & Kouser, R. (2013). Impact of quality corporate governance on firm performance: a ten year perspective. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*, 7 (3), 656-670.
- Babic, V. (2003). Corporate governance problems in transition economies in *Winston-Salem: Wake Forest University (Social Science Research Seminar)*, http://www.ibrarian.net/navon/paper/corporate_governance_problems_in_transition_econo.pdf?paperid=3696120
- Baydoun, N., Maguire, W., Ryan, N., & Willett, R. (2013). Corporate governance in five Arabian Gulf countries, *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 28 (1), 7–22.
- Butt, A. S. (2012). *Corporate governance for Pakistan (4th edition)* Azeem Academy.
- Cheng, S., Evans, J. H. & Nagarajan, N. J. (2008). Board size and firm performance: The moderating effects of the market for corporate control. *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting*, 31(2), 121-145.
- Ekanayake, A., Perera, H., & Perera, S. (2010). Contextual relativity of the role of accounting in Corporate governance: evidence from the banking industry in Sri Lanka. *The Sixth Asia Pacific Interdisciplinary Research in Accounting Conference, Sydney*, 1-27,
- Ghabayen, M. A. (2012). Board characteristics and firm performance: Case of Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, 2 (2), 168-200.
- Jensen, C. M., & Meckling, H. W. (1976). Theory of the firm: managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305-360.
- John, K., Litov, L. P. & Yeung, B.Y. (2005). Corporate governance and managerial risk-taking: theory and evidence. *Working paper*.
- Mallin, C. A. (2004). *Corporate governance*, 1th edn, Oxford University Press, Incorporated.
- Mayers, D., & C. W. Smith, C. W. (2010). Compensation and board structure: evidence from the insurance industry. *Journal of Risk and Insurance*, 77(2), 297-327.

- Nestor, S., & Thompson, J. (2000). Corporate governance patterns in OECD economies: is convergence under way?. OECD (2001), *Corporate governance in Asia: A comparative perspective*, 19-41, OECD, Paris.
- Owen, J. (2003). The Failure of HIH Insurance: A corporate collapse and its lessons, Common wealth of Australia. *HIH Royal Commission Report*, Speech to 13th common wealth Law Conference, 1.
- Reed, D. (2002). Corporate governance reforms in developing countries. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 37 (3), 223-247.
- Roggi, O., Garvey, M., & Damodaran, A. (2012). *Risk Taking: A Corporate Governance Perspective*. New York: University Stern School of Business.
- Rogers, D. (2002). Does executive portfolio structure effect risk management? CEO risk taking incentives and corporate derivatives usage. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 26(2), 271-295.
- Saito, T. (2008). Family firms and firm performance: Evidence from Japan. *Journal of the Japanese and International Economies*, 22(4), 620-646.
- Sharabati, A. A., Jawad, S. N. & Bontis, N. (2010). Intellectual capital and business performance in the pharmaceutical sector of Jordan, *Management Decision*, 48(1), 105-131.
- Sharpe, I. G., & Stadnik, A. (2007). Financial distress in Australian general insurers. *Journal of Risk and Insurance*, 74(2), 377-399.
- Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R.W. (1997). A survey of corporate governance. *Journal of Finance*, 52(2), 737-783.
- Solomon, J., & Solomon, A. (2004). *Corporate governance and accountability*, John Wiley, New York, NY.
- Ullah, M., Hashim, M., Khan, A.M., & Safi, W. (2017). Does corporate governance affects risk: a case of listed firms on Pakistan Stock Exchange. *City University Research Journal*, 21 - 26.
- Wahla, K., Shah, S. Z. A., & Hussain, Z. (2012). Impact of ownership structure on firm performance: evidence from non-financial listed companies at Karachi stock exchange. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 84. 6-13.

Mahboob Ullah
Associate Professor,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
Al-Taqwa University, Nangarhar, Afghanistan.
Email: mahboobmails@gmail.com

Niaz Mohammad Hamdard
Assistant Professor
Faculty of Public Administration and Policy
Nangarhar University, Afghanistan
Email: niazmhs@yahoo.com

Noor Ahmad Sahar
Assistant professor
Faculty of Public Administration and policy
Nangarhar University, Afghanistan
noorahmadsahar@gmail.com

© 2019 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

